

MORE IS MORE OR LESS IS MORE? INFLUENCE OF TRAINING DURATION ON
LEARNING NOISE-VOCODED SPEECH

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I. Introduction

Listeners are not always exposed to ideal listening conditions or clear speech signals, yet they are still able to comprehend what is being said. Normal Hearing listeners (NH) have an easier time adapting quickly to ambiguous speech signals, accented speech or speech in a noisy situation. This ability to adjust to unfamiliar speech patterns and signals can be attributed to the natural practice listeners get from everyday life experiences. Similarly, if the acoustic signal is distorted or manipulated, an individual can rely on their speech perception skills to help them adjust to the low-quality speech presentation. Speech perception allows us to interpret and understand utterances across a variety of turbulent environments and adverse circumstances (Corps & Rabagliati, 2020). This process explains how an individual is able to understand an auditory signal by identifying the linguistic structures and speech sounds in the signal and associate this information to word recognition. Although NH listeners may have an easier time adjusting to speech variability such as accents, other patient populations may have harder time distinguishing speech sounds and thus will have a harder time with speech comprehension. A cochlear implant has a limited number of electrodes that are responsible for interpreting the incoming auditory signals and are supposed to help distinguish the subtle difference speakers may produce. While some CI users adjust to their devices quickly and thus adapt to speech variability they are presented with, other CI users struggle to keep up. Similarly, a non-native language speakers will be at a disadvantaged in speech perception tasks due to the adverse conditions and the lack of lexical knowledge (Lecumberri et al., 2010).

Speakers develop an enhanced sensitivity to their own native language that allows them to discriminate and categorize speech sounds and words. It has been widely assumed that non-native speakers will process an unambiguous speech sound by comparing the noise to their own phonetic category inventory (Pajak & Levy, 2014). Essentially, a listener who has very little experience hearing non-native sounds will attempt to translate this unfamiliar sound and map it on to an acoustically or articulatory familiar sound from their own language, if available. The similarity between non-native sounds and native sounds can directly impact an individual's ability to discriminate. For example, at times non-native speakers are tasked with discriminating between two non-native sounds but it is difficult for them to compare these sounds against their own phonetic category because in their own language these sounds are not distinguishable or rather, they lack acoustic variation. A widely known example is that Japanese speakers who learn English as their second language struggle to differentiate between the /r/ and /l/. This perceptual challenge arises because Japanese speakers acclimate both sounds into one category, whereas in the US these sounds are separated.

Noise vocoded sentences are used to simulate the acoustic information and/or signal heard by cochlear implant (CI) users (Shannon et al., 1995). The noise-vocoding process takes the original speech signal, severely reduces spectral resolution, eliminates periodicity, creates amplitude changes, and divides the signal into a set of separate frequency bands in order to produce a new noise-vocoded signal (McGettigan et al., 2014). Manipulating speech to be considered noise-vocoded decreases the intelligibility of the spoken word or phrase, thus eliciting the need to train individuals in order to increase speech comprehension. Individuals with cochlear implants are limited in terms

of number of electrodes that they have available to process auditory signals. Additionally, CI users can be tasked with adapting to speech quality that can be less than ideal. Past research has emphasized the importance of perceptual learning on enhancing speech perception using auditory training. Perceptual learning refers to the concept that with trained exposure, individuals are able to make changes to their perceptual system which allows them to differentiate confounding speech stimuli and adjust to novel acoustic signals and/or talkers (Goldstone, 1998). One way that speech comprehension can be tested is when listeners are given the task to interpret noise-vocoded speech. Noise-vocoded speech can be difficult to understand initially because it conveys phonetic information that is mainly conveyed through temporal-cues instead of spectral cues (Roberts et al., 2005). The lack of spectral information can make tasks such as talker identification or speech comprehension much harder for cochlear implant users causing them to perform poorly as compared to others (Loebach et al., 2008). Individuals who are diagnosed with some type or degree of hearing loss (HL) and are assigned to hearing devices such as cochlear implants require training and an adjustment period. These devices require the individual to rely on professionals to help them adapt to their new hearing limitations. Aural rehabilitation (AR) is directed at lessening the difficulties associated with HL and avoiding the consequences that occur when hearing losses are left untreated. AR aims at providing individuals with the training needed to restore their ability to effectively listen and communicate with their partners. Clinicians are typically faced with the issue of appropriately designing training programs for their clients. This includes multiple factors to consider such as training duration, however a clear and evidence supported training rate is yet to be established (Fu & Galvin, 2007). CI users all

vary in terms of how much time it takes them to adjust to their herding device and how much progress they make once they start their rehabilitation process. Not to mention, CI users struggle with training and testing due to their underdeveloped or non-existent speech patterns which leads them to require intensive speech production training in order to restore and/or develop skills that would allow them to perform better (Fu, Galvin, Wang, & Nogaki et al., 2005).

One form of training that is often proposed in rehabilitation plans is auditory training, which is a type of training that aims at enhancing or developing a listener's ability to recognize speech in the auditory signal. There are two types of auditory training: bottom-up (also referred to analytic training) and top-down (also referred to as synthetic training) training. The bottom-up approach suggests that listeners should focus on the details that differentiate an acoustic signal whereas the top-down approach suggests that listeners should focus on the whole structure and should use context to aid in the speech comprehension process (Drouin & Theodore, 2020). In other words, bottom-up processing implies using sensory information to assess and assimilate information while top-down processing relies on using past knowledge and stored information to interpret a visual or acoustic cues. Both types of auditory training have the advantages and disadvantages in helping CI users interpret speech, but both are involved in speech comprehension. Studies using noise-vocoded sentences and NH listeners allow us to understand more about how speech perception skills are improved and how these types of auditory training play a role in learning and changes to our perceptual system.

A. Importance of lexical knowledge and top-down processing

Adapting to unfamiliar or distorted signals involves adaptation and requires that listeners use lexical information to attach meaning to the spoken phrase. Top-down processing makes up for the challenges deteriorated speech causes, in terms of speech comprehension (Fu & Galvin, 2007) and this type of processing is typically recruited by listeners to successfully recognize speech in noise and across a variety of spoken language tasks (Casserly & Barney, 2017). Improvements in perceptual learning can involve the use of multiple mechanisms and lexical knowledge. Davis, Johnsrude, and Hervais-Adelman (2005) conducted a series of five experiments to understand the impact lexical information had on normal hearing listeners' ability to understand noise-vocoded stimulations and what processes were contributing to this adaptation. In each experiment, the conditions were manipulated to determine the crucial elements needed to enhance perceptual learning for distorted speech. The first experiment focused on showcasing that with a few minutes of exposure to noise-vocoded sentences, intelligibility of degraded speech increases. Participants were presented with distorted sentences and were asked to write down as much of the sentence as they heard. With time and repeated exposure, changes to the participant's perceptual abilities were evident and listeners were able to report correct responses; thus, indicating that speech intelligibility can improve once the individuals receive more practice. To further understand what processes drive perceptual learning, Davis et al. (2005) implemented the presence of feedback as listeners worked on improving their ability to understand vocoded speech. Participants were placed in either one of two conditions: the distorted-clear-distorted (DCD) group or the distorted-distorted-clear (DDC) group. During this phase, it was predicted that those who heard a clear presentation of the phrase in between the distorted presentations, would have an

easier time transcribing the sentence. This hypothesis was supported by the concept referred to as the “pop-out” effect, which suggests that the insertion of clear speech provides listeners with the much-needed context to make the distorted speech much more intelligible. Receiving this type of feedback in the second presentation allowed for an increase in speech comprehension. These findings promote the effectiveness of the DCD presentation as well as the influence of relying on higher level processing. Top-down processing not only influences the perceptual pop-out effect, but it also enables advancements in perceptual learning and the increased ability to understand distorted sentences (Corps & Rabagliati, 2020).

To further explore the effectiveness of providing feedback, participants were placed into another experimental group where they received written feedback. The purpose of this condition was to exhibit if written feedback could be just as influential and impactful as acoustic feedback had been in improving the speech recognition skills of the participants. The participants were either presented with distorted-written-distorted (DWD) sentences or with two distorted (DD) sentences. The results of the third experiment demonstrated that the feedback is not limited to the acoustic form, written feedback can also lead to significant gains in perceptual learning of vocoded speech. The extra visual cues that written text provides help disambiguate the degraded speech (Pilling & Thomas, 2011). These findings prompted the next series of experiments to further understand how utilizing lexical information helps improve an individual's ability to process and comprehend noise-vocoded sentences. Participants were presented with real English sentences while others were trained and assessed using non-word sentences using the distorted-clear -distorted format (while also receiving written feedback), similar

to previous experiments. The results reported by (Davis et al., 2005) conveyed that although some gains are seen through the presentation of nonword sentences, lexical information plays a critical role in enhancing perceptual learning of noise video speech. The lack of real English words present in the nonword sentences contributed to the missing top-down support that NH listeners typically rely on in order to comprehend altered speech signals. For top-down processing to be effective and influence perceptual learning, a speaker must be able to associate the distorted version of speech to the clear version, thus proving that being able to identify the vocoded speech allows for rapid learning (Corps & Rabagliati, 2020). Although these findings imply that lexical information, as well as semantic-level meaning and/or syntactic information provide the necessary guidance for improved speech recognition, the question still remains as to which of the three is the driving factor behind these changes. Davis et al. (2005) pushed the next experiment one step further by analyzing the importance of syntactic information in order to determine if sentence-level meaning is a key element for learning. The results indicated that lexical information is a decisive factor in perceptual learning and syntactic content is not considered as effective at producing learning gains.

A key factor that can help listeners determine unfamiliar and novel speech is the use of higher-level knowledge. In a series of three experiments, Corps and Rabagliati (2020) investigated how high-level knowledge aids perceptual learning of distorted speech and if listeners used high-lexical knowledge to generate predictions about upcoming semantic content or sentence form. In each experiment participants listened to question-answer scenarios and were asked to type what they had heard when the answer was presented. The questions were clearly spoken whereas the answers were presented as

noise-vocoded responses. To evaluate if the form of a question impacted speech recognition, the questions were either presented in a form constraining manner, meaning that only one answer correctly satisfied the demand of question. An example a form constraining question would be, “Which space ranger stared in Toy Story?” On the other hand, subjects could also be presented with form unconstraining questions, meaning the question was open-ended and could elicit multiple correct responses. For example, a form unconstraining question would be, “What is your favorite animated character?” In terms of the answers, these were either semantically consistent and evidently answered the intended question (ex. Buzz Lightyear) or the answer was semantically inconsistent and made no sense (The Eiffel Tower). Each group was given a set of question-answer scenarios, there were four conditions total: two groups received from constraining questions and were either presented with semantically consistent or inconsistent answers. The two remaining groups received unconstraining inquires while also receiving either semantically inconsistent or consistent answers. The study attempted to define the relationship between question constraint and answer consistency, which would be determined if subjects used form predictions or semantic predictions to anticipate and understand upcoming distorted speech. Seeing as how subjects can make semantic or form predictions to interpret the distorted speech, the first experiment intended to establish to what extent does the use of high-level knowledge promote speech recognition. Throughout this experiment, there was a chance that response bias could affect what the listeners reported. Meaning, if participants were exposed to a constrained question followed by a semantically consistent answer, then for future stimuli they might always expect the answer to be semantically correct causing low report scores when the

answer is semantically inconsistent. To combat response biases a signal detection analysis was used to determine participants' sensitivity to the words they actually heard in the distorted answer (Corps & Rabagliati, 2020). Experiment 1 showcased that participants were better at reporting vocoded answers when they were semantically consistent or related with the question rather than semantically inconsistent. However, this experiment highlighted that the form of the sentence, whether it is constrained or unconstrained, does not affect how well people are able to interpret the vocoded answer.

For the second experiment, Corps and Rabagliati (2020) used a similar design to Distorted-Clear-distorted condition done in the (Davis et al., 2005) study, in order to investigate whether learning is enhanced by prediction associated with form or meaning and to further examine what role top-down support played on learning. For this condition, listeners heard a distorted phrase and disclosed what they heard. Next, they heard a clear question followed by the same distorted phrase as before, however, this time it was used as an answer to the question. Indeed, the results indicated similar findings of experiment 1, seeing as how presenting the distorted phrase twice helped with the listener make a semantically related prediction about the upcoming phrase. Hearing a semantically consistent response to the question was presented allowed for perceptual learning to play a key role in processing the degraded speech. Higher-lexical information made interpreting distorted speech easier, and it prompted semantic predictions to be made about the upcoming distorted speech phrases. Thus experiment 1 and 2 convey that being able to predict the semantic content of the upcoming distorted phrase seems to be a critical factor in understanding altered speech, unlike form predictions. The design of experiment 3 included similar stimulus from experiments 1 and 2 however, for this third condition

the semantically consistent answer was heard in a later trial rather than immediately after the related constrained or unconstrained question. Contrary to the findings in the first two experiments, the results of this last condition indicated that the listeners had improved in terms of reporting correct distorted answers and being able to predict sentence form had been a useful element in improving noise-vocoded speech comprehension and learning. Additionally, participants were evidently better at understanding degraded speech by the third experiment, which further proves that with training and exposing listeners to a decent amount of vocoded speech, speech that initially seemed unintelligible becomes easier to process (Davis et al., 2005). The long delay in between presentation of the clear questions and distorted answers increased the effectiveness of form predictions and allowed for more contextual support to be provided towards semantically inconsistent distorted answers. High-level knowledge allowed for listeners to adapt to noise-vocoded sentences and emphasized the influence that semantic predictions (as well as form predictions) can have on learning and recognition.

B. Importance of indexical knowledge and its influence on speech perception

On the other hand, other researchers have proposed that it is important to look at the indexical information that an acoustic speech signal carries in order to understand how individuals are able to comprehend speech and distinguish or identify talkers. Loebach et al. (2008) designed a study in which individuals were trained to improve their talker identification skills to see if this training could be applied to the process of clearly recognizing degraded non-trained degraded words and sentences. While Davis et al. (2005) focused on showcasing the importance of lexical information, this study aimed to

investigate the impact that indexical information has on improving speech recognition and learning. Additionally, several studies have demonstrated the significance of providing stimuli that engages the individual and captures their full attention in order for the training to be effective. For example, Huyck and Johnsrude (2012) trained a group of participants to listen to noise-vocoded sentences while focusing on one of three items. One group just had to focus on the spoken speech, another group was instructed to focus on a visual distraction, and the other was instructed to focus on an auditory distractor. Each group was then tasked with reporting what they had heard and was given no feedback. The subjects in the conditions with distractors were simultaneously exposed to degraded speech while also still attending to their non-linguistic tasks. The test phase was conducted without any distractions and the group that showed the most gains and benefit from training was the group tasked with focusing on the degraded speech itself. These results support the idea that passive listening is not enough to make great improvements to an individual's speech processing performance (Fu & Galvin, 2007).

Participants in the (Loebach et al., 2008) study were distributed in three groups: talker identification (ID), gender identification (ID) and a transcription group and it was predicted that subjects in the talker ID condition would outperform those in the gender ID condition because it requires more attention to recognize a talker. The participants' stimuli for the pre and post-test assessment consisted of Low-Predictability sentences (context is uninformative) and Anomalous sentences (words in sentence are semantically unrelated). The items used in the training phase were high predictability sentences (context is semantically associated). Feedback was only provided during the training phase. Further training varied between groups, seeing as how those in the transcription

condition had to complete a transcription task, those in the gender identification group were asked to identify their speaker as being either a male or female and those in the talker identification task were presented with different names and had to determine who the speaker was. In other words, the gender ID and talker ID tasks weren't lexically orientated. Accuracy was based on the final words identified and reported in these different types of sentences. Pre-test and post-test results were used to see if the results could be generalized. In other words, post-training gains would be evident if accuracy scores were higher in post-test because it would indicate that the individuals are able to apply the training gains into speech comprehension involving altered speech. The results of this experiment conveyed that the type of training participants received impacted the results, as shown by the fact that the transcription group and the talker identification group performed better than the gender identification group. Those in the talker ID group had to pay more attention to the acoustic differences between speakers and thus had higher task demands than those in the gender ID group. Subjects in the transcription group were expected to do well because their training tasks required deep processing and was a traditional lexical task, however, those in the talker ID group were able to perform just as well. These results provide evidence that indexical tasks can require speedy analyzation and processing skills that also contribute to long-lasting perceptual learning and speech recognition abilities. This implies that when indexical tasks require controlled attention from the recipient, the tasks can be just as effective for perceptual learning as lexical tasks (Loebach et al., 2008). Furthermore, it is suggested that utilizing (or analyzing) both lexical and indexical information contributes to better speech comprehension of the acoustic signal.

C. Implications from previous training programs

As shown by the evidence above, most of the research out there discusses how NH listeners are able to make improvements once they've received some training. Despite the immense and inevitable variability in speech perception outcomes for CI users produce, Drouin and Theodore (2020) suggested that it is still important to understand how this population will react to specific training programs. Due to this, Fu et al. (2005) wanted to see if CI users could also benefit from auditory training to improve their speech recognition skills and if their speech recognition skills could be improved via an electronic modality instead of in-person training. Participants were CI users who had poor to moderate speech recognition abilities and were trained using phonemic contrast tasks in which they were asked to distinguish between 1000 monosyllabic words and 200 nonwords. In these scenarios either vowels or constants become the targeted phoneme and listeners were asked to discriminate between different sounds being presented to them. Through this bottom-up approach listeners were tasked with attending to small acoustic differences in speech stimuli (Fu & Galvin, 2007). As subjects' performance improved, the acoustics differences between stimuli were reduced and/or the number of response choices was increased (Fu et al. 2005). In other words, listeners were being presented with words that only slightly differed, for example: *sit vs sat or can vs ban*. The reduced phonemic variability forced participants to focus on the words being presented in order to catch the subtle differences. The listeners were expected to train once a week for an hour, five days a week for four weeks. The findings of this experiment showcased highly varied improvement by the participants seeing as how some individuals

demonstrated notable improvement after only 2 weeks while others improved towards the end of the training experiment. According to previous research, (Fu et al., 2005) moderate auditory training can provide beneficial gains for CI users, although intensive training programs might result in better and more consistent results. Similarly, other studies have also implied that there should a greater importance placed on the quality of the stimuli being used for training than the time commitment listeners put into the training program, (Fu & Galvin, 2007).

Altogether these findings suggest that auditory training can be an efficient way of improving speech recognition skills and it can influence gains made by rehabilitation patients however, many factors are left unresolved such as the amount of training individuals should receive in order for training to be effective. Previous research has focused on understanding how listeners perceive noise-vocoded speech whereas this study will attempt to define the optimal parameters that are needed to make training successful. This experiment will look at the effect of predictability and the effect created by manipulating training duration across three groups.

Despite its clinical relevance, there is currently limited research out there that answers the question regarding the ideal amount of training individuals should receive in order to develop or enhance their speech perception skills. In the following study, we attempted to systematically control the amount of training and determine if the amount of training matters. As discussed above, previous studies have used inconsistent trial numbers and so, it's difficult to determine how much training is necessary. Although it has been established that auditory training is effective at improving degraded speech comprehension, it is currently unknown how much of this training is necessary to secure

gains. Knowing how much auditory training one should provide or recommend to their patients is fundamentally crucial, yet this area of research has many unanswered questions that require further investigation. The lack of information creates a problem for clinicians who want to recommend an auditory training program to help cochlear implant patients adjust to their devices and improve their speech recognition skills. The goal for many clinicians is to implement a rehabilitation process that will maximize spoken language comprehension and support the auditory needs of different patient population such as CI users.

D. The current study

In the current study, three groups of normal hearing listeners completed a speech recognition task across three different phases in which they were exposed to noise vocoded sentences. To help compare the results produced by the participants and to determine the effect of different training periods a pretest-posttest design was implemented. Listeners were tested prior to the start of their training to establish a baseline of their ability to understand degraded speech signals and then they were tested immediately after training to see if there had been any changes to their speech recognition capabilities. For pretest and posttest, listeners were tasked with transcribing what they heard, and their transcription would later be analyzed for keywords. All participants received the same amount of pre-and post-test items regardless of which group they belonged to and received no feedback. However, the amount of stimuli each group was assigned to differed significantly between the three groups during training. During the training phase of this experiment, listeners heard high-predictability (HP) and low-predictability (LP) sentences and received feedback. The Short Training Group, was set

to receive 80 items (20 LP sentences and 60 HP sentences). The Medium Training Group, was designated to receive 160 items (40 LP sentences and 120 HP sentences) and the Long Training Group was set to receive 240 items (60 LP sentences and 180 HP sentences). Throughout the training phases, listeners were not asked to transcribe instead, they were given two sentences and had to decide between the two options which one did they hear. During the testing phase of this experiment, listeners were presented with anomalous (AN), high-predictability (HP), and low-predictability (LP) sentences. We included trained stimuli at each test to assess how well the participants were able to retain the speech recognition skills they gained throughout the training phase and novel items to eliminate the potential problem that participants had memorized the answers to the trained items. The stimuli presented to the participants was spoken by five talkers each from a different region in the US. Exposing listeners to multiple talkers has been proven to provide many benefits, seeing as how it allows participants to practice adjusting to different pronunciations and thus results can be generalized, and it makes learning more effective (Cassery & Barney, 2017). Multiple studies have shown that repeated exposure to auditory training improves a listener's ability to adapt to noise-vocoded speech. The current study aimed to expand upon previous findings and wanted to determine the ideal training parameters that would produce the most gain. The idea driving this study was to understand how much auditory training is needed to see improvements in normal listeners' speech perception and to compare performance between the different types of sentences. These findings could provide useful insight that can be applied to translational rehabilitation for patients adapting to degraded speech signals in terms of knowing how much auditory training is sufficient to improve their speech recognition skills.

One of the goals for this study was to discover how much training does an individual have to undergo to improve their perception of the noise-vocoded speech. Currently, it is unclear what parameters to set when designing a treatment plan for individuals seeking auditory training. This information is important to understand in the context of building an aural rehabilitation plan for patients with hearing loss, hearing aid users or cochlear implant users. Past research findings have focused on finding out what drives perceptual learning of degraded speech or trying to define what factors impact comprehension when the acoustic signal is distorted. Throughout this study, we sought to understand the optimal training parameters for auditory training that led to the most growth and produced beneficial gains. We hypothesized that the more training the participants received the better they would become at comprehending and adapting to noise vocoded speech, thus their performance in the post-test phase would be higher than the other groups who received less training. Essentially, we predicted that the group that would be presented with the highest amount of training would outperform the groups who received less training. These results would support the idea that a substantial amount of repeated exposure produces higher performance in speech recognition tasks and overall better adaptation to noise-vocoded speech. Alternatively, if the amount of training is not as important as we had estimated then the listener's performance may reflect a plateau effect in terms of comprehension benefit after experiencing a short amount of training. Meaning, if the training group that received the smallest amount of training performs better than the group with the most exposure to distorted acoustic signals, then this will prove that less training is better and more effective. These results would be

consistent and support the idea that auditory training does not require a large amount of auditory training.

Another goal that this study addressed is the difference in performance between the different types of sentences. We implemented low-predictability sentences to determine how well participants could understand a sentence that lacked contextual information. Anomalous sentences contain real English words; however, they are semantically unrelated and syntactically correct. At pre-test it is believed that participants would perform poorly across all sentence types due to the lack of exposure to the degraded speech signal. After training we hypothesized that there would be an improvement for all three types of sentences, but accuracy for HP sentences would still outperform the results from the LP and AN sentence. This goal looked at determining the effect of predictability. Meaning, we wanted to assess if the presence of context, or on the other hand the absence of it, affected the listeners ability to correctly identify the correct keywords in each sentence. These results would indicate that training and receiving feedback in the training phase does contribute to the adaptation of degraded speech signals across a variety of sentence types (Norris et al., 2003).

II. Methods

A. Participants

Participants (n= 90) were adults between 18 and 36 years of age (mean age = 29 years) who were recruited from the Prolific participant pool (<https://www.prolific.co>). Participants were randomly assigned to one of three training groups (n = 30 in each training group). We used the Prolific filter option to limit participants who entered the

study therefore only those who self-reported that they were monolingual speakers of English, had no history of language or hearing related disorder, and identified being from one of several regions of the US were selected for the study. All participants were subjected to a headphone screening prior to the start of each experimental phase (Woods et al., 2017). Participants were given three attempts to put on their headphones, and if they did not pass the headphone check they were excluded from the next phase. After the data was collected, 81 participants passed the screening (Short group $n = 28$, Medium group $n = 29$, Long group $n = 24$).

B. Stimuli

The stimuli used in this study were obtained from the Nationwide Speech Project (NSP), a corpus of spoken language (Clopper & Pisoni, 2006). This corpus contained several speech samples from adult female and male talkers who had recorded different types of phrases and words that are accessible for research purposes. Five talkers from different regions across the US were chosen (3 females; 2 males) from this corpus to produce the different types of sentences. Stimuli consisted of high-predictability ($n = 90$) and low-predictability sentences ($n = 30$), as well as anomalous sentences ($n = 40$). Sentences consisted of 4 - 8 words. We analyzed each sentence and looked at each keyword. High-predictability sentences contain semantically correlated information/context which increases the probability of anticipating the words within the sentence, especially the final word (ex. Eve was made from Adam's rib). For the low-predictability sentences, the final word was not as easily anticipated (ex. She hopes Jane

called about the calf). The anomalous (atypical) sentences consisted of words that did not contain a semantic relationship, in other the words had no meaningful correlation, but they were syntactically correct (ex. The arm is riding on the bench). Figure 1 displays sentence distribution across all three periods of this study. We presented novel anomalous sentences during the testing phase, which included the pre-test and post-test. Low-predictability and high-predictability sentences were presented during all three periods of this study, pre-test, training, and post-test. During the training period HP and LP sentences were novel and during the test phases these sentences were classified as trained. During the training period sentences were presented twice, essentially all of the stimuli was doubled in order to give the participants enough practice.

Using the Praat software (Boersma, 2001), the chosen sentences from the NSP corpus were modified to remove prolonged silences and remove any unnecessary background noise. The selected sentences were then noise-vocoded using an 8 non-linearly spaced channels based on the Greenwood function (Greenwood, 1990) using the Angel Sim Software (Smart & Frisch, 2015). The lower frequency band was set at 200 Hz and the upper frequency band was set at 7000 Hz and we used a 24 dB/octave cut off. Using Praat, sound files were then RMS normalized using the rescale intensity function and intensity was scaled at 70 dB for all files.

C. Procedures

This study was approved by the Institutional Review Board at California State University Fullerton. The experiment was presented on the Gorilla web-based platform. All participants were presented with a consent form before they took part in the

experiment. Following the consent form, all participants had to undergo a headphone check to ensure that they were wearing headphones before they proceeded with the rest of the experiment. This study required that subjects always had headphones on in order to hear the auditory stimuli better. Additionally, it was required that the subjects in this experiment type their responses using a keyboard on their electronic device.

This study consisted of two testing phases and one training phase, which is reflected on Figure 2. The training period consisted of three training groups who were all exposed to different training durations. The experiment was composed of pre-test, training, and an immediate post-test; all three phases would take about 45 minutes to complete. The responses from the subjects would remain anonymous. Participants were randomly assigned to one of three training groups: short, medium, or long. All groups received similar stimuli the only difference was the amount of stimuli they were exposed to.

	Pre-Test	Training	Post-Test
High-Predictability "That job was an easy task"			
Low-Predictability "Peter could consider the dove"			
Anomalous "The sink served with an easy flame"			

Figure 1: Distribution of item type across all three phases of the experiment. At pre-test and post-test, participants were exposed to all three different types of sentences (high-predictability, low-predictability, and anomalous sentences). At training, participants only heard two different types of sentences (low-predictability and high-predictability).

Figure 2: The current study consisted of three phases: pre-test, training, and post-test. At pre-test and post-test participants did not receive feedback but at training, participants were given feedback. During both testing periods, participants were presented with a noise-vocoded sentence and a transcription task. At training, participants were presented with a noise-vocoded sentence and with a multiple-choice task; where they were tasked with selecting which of the two sentences they had just heard.

Figure 2 provides a representation of what participants encountered during the training period of this study. During the training phase, the participants were exposed to a noise-vocoded speech signal and then two written options were displayed on the screen from which the participants were tasked with selecting the phrase they thought they heard. The participants in the training period were provided with feedback on whether their response was right or wrong. A progress bar was also included so that participants could see how much they had finished and how much they still needed to complete. The

purpose of the training group was to drill participants with different amounts of stimuli in order to improve speech recognition skills. This period of exposure allowed participants to adapt to different types of speakers (adult male or female) from different regions across the US. The regions included the Western, Southern, Northern, New England, and Midland area. The goal of this repeated exposure was to promote learning that would then generalize to the post-test. In training, participants heard three different amounts of sentences produced by five talkers. In the short training group participants heard 80 sentences, meaning that each talker produced 16 sentences. Participants in the medium training group heard 160 sentences, meaning each talker produced 32 sentences. The subjects in long training group heard 240 sentences, which meant that every talker produced 48 sentences. The total number of sentences and distribution of each item type across each training group is displayed on Figure 3.

Two test phases were administered. A pre-test was conducted to establish a baseline of the participants speech recognition skills prior to training and a post-test was issued immediately after training to determine the effect of training. This pretest-posttest design was implemented to showcase and analyze the effect of training, in other words, this design was done to showcase the participant's improvement. We used equal proportion of high-predictability, low-predictability, and anomalous sentences at each test, which resulted in 40 test items (5 low-predictability, 15 high-predictability, 20 anomalous sentences). The LP and HP sentences were trained, and the anomalous sentences were novel. Despite the fact that participants belonged to different training groups, the test phase was identical for all participants. First, participants heard a noise-vocoded sentence produced by one of five talkers. Next, the participants were presented

with the question “What did you hear?” Following this question, participants were asked to type their response in the textbox and pressed the enter key to register their transcription. Participants were asked to guess any words in the sentence if they were unsure of what they heard.

Each sentence from pre-test and post-test was scored for accuracy by analyzing the participant’s transcription and looking at each word individually. We considered every keyword for each sentence presented during the testing phase of this study, so for some sentences the number of keywords was longer (maximum number of keywords was 8). Essentially, every sentence and transcribed word was examined to determine the number of keywords the participants got correct. A point was awarded for every correct keyword and zero points were awarded if the participant’s transcription was incorrect. The number of correct keywords was totaled for each sentence. A response was considered correct if the transcription was the exact same spelling of the word or if it’s the same word but a different spelling. For example, if a participant wrote *their* instead of *there*, the participant would still receive credit for the word. The participants did not receive any credit if they did not correctly transcribe any of the keywords we were looking for or if they left their responses blank. To be more specific, if a participant wrote *beats*, but the keyword was *beads*, they would not get a point for the word they transcribed because the /t/ phoneme changed the meaning of the keyword we were looking for. The sentences were scored and given credit even if they contained misspellings, typos, and alternate spellings as long as these misspelling did not change the meaning of the word and/or produce a new real word. A deletion or addition of a grapheme was permitted as long as the keyword still carried the same meaning. For

example, if the target sentence was *cut the meat into small chunks*, then all of the following are examples of acceptable responses for the keyword *small*: *smalj*, *smallj*, and *smal*. The following are examples of unacceptable responses for the keyword *small*: *smaller*, *mall*, *smalls*, and *smallest*. The training phase of this study did not consist of a transcription task, so this grading format did not apply to the responses given at training.

Figure 3: Distribution of training duration/dosage across all three groups. The Short Training Group received a total of 80 sentences consisting of 20 Low-Predictability (LP) and 60 High-Predictability (HP) sentences. The Medium Training Group received a total of 160 sentences consisting of 40 Low-Predictability (LP) and 120 High-Predictability (HP) sentences. The Long Training Group received a total of 240 sentences consisting of 60 Low-Predictability (LP) and 180 High-Predictability (HP) sentences. The number of sentences was tripled from short to long training group. Anomalous sentences (Novel) were excluded from the training phase.

III. Results

A. Training

Figure 4 shows the mean accuracy of training across participants for the three training groups. We examined mean accuracy for both low predictability and high predictability sentences. Visual inspection reveals that all three training groups performed near ceiling on the task.

Figure 4: Training accuracy for low predictability and high predictability sentences during training for the short training group (purple), medium training group (green), and long training group (blue). Error bars indicate standard error of the mean. Accuracy was near ceiling across training groups.

To examine this pattern statistically, trial-level responses (0 = incorrect, 1 = correct) were submitted to a generalized linear mixed effects model (GLMM) with the binomial response family implemented in the lme4 package in R (Bates et al., 2015). The Satterthwaite approximation of degrees of freedom was used to evaluate statistical significance using lmerTest (Kuznetsova et al., 2017). The fixed effect of training group

(treatment-coded, with the short training group as the reference level) and sentence predictability (dummy-coded; 0 = low predictability sentences, 1 = high predictability sentences) were entered into the model. The random effects structure consisted of random intercepts by subject, random intercepts by sentence, and random intercepts by talker. There were no statistically reliable differences in training accuracy between the short training group and medium training group ($\hat{\beta} = -0.480$, $SE = 0.965$, $z = -0.498$, $p = 0.619$), nor were there statistically reliable differences in training accuracy between the short training group and the long training group ($\hat{\beta} = -1.063$, $SE = 0.917$, $z = -1.159$, $p = 0.246$). In addition, we observed no statistically reliable difference in accuracy for low predictability compared to high predictability sentences ($\hat{\beta} = 0.758$, $SE = 0.891$, $z = 0.851$, $p = 0.395$). There were no statistically reliable two-way interactions. The results from the training analysis indicate that all three training groups showed equivalent performance and there were no differences in accuracy across sentence predictability. The full analyses are shown in Table I.

B. Test

Accuracy at test was based on proportion correct words in each sentence. Proportion accuracy scores were calculated for each sentence for every participant and were relative to the number of words in each sentence. Figure 5 shows mean proportion correct accuracy for trained sentences for the short, medium, and long training groups and sentence predictability types. Visual inspection reveals listeners showed poorer accuracy at pre-test relative to post-test and that all groups improved following training. Accuracy appears comparable across training groups and item types. Figure 6 shows

mean proportion correct accuracy for novel sentences (anomalous) for the short, medium, and long training groups. Participants appear to show poorer performance at pre-test relative to post-test and each training appears to show comparable performance at each time point that improves after training.

To examine this pattern statistically, proportion correct trial-level responses were submitted to a linear mixed effects model (LMER). The Satterthwaite approximation of degrees of freedom was used to evaluate statistical significance using `lmerTest` (Kuznetsova et al., 2017). We ran one model for trained sentences and a separate model for novel sentences. For the trained sentences, the model included the fixed effect of training group (treatment-coded, with the short training group as the reference level), test session (dummy-coded; 0 = pre-test, 1 = post-test), and sentence predictability (dummy-coded; 0 = low predictability sentences, 1 = high predictability sentences). The random effects structure consisted of random intercepts by subject, random intercepts by sentence, and random intercepts by talker, as well as random slopes by subject for test session and predictability. There were no statistically reliable differences between the short group and the medium training group ($\hat{\beta} = 0.007$, $SE = 0.034$, $t = 0.214$, $p = 0.831$) nor was there a statistically reliable difference between the short group and the long group ($\hat{\beta} = 0.007$, $SE = 0.035$, $t = 0.204$, $p = 0.837$). There was a statistically significant effect of test session ($\hat{\beta} = 0.127$, $SE = 0.016$, $t = 7.717$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that participants showed higher performance at post-test compared to pre-test. All other two- and three-way interactions were not statistically reliable (see Table II for model output).

Figure 5: Mean proportion accuracy for trained sentences for each of the three training groups for low predictability and high predictability sentences. Performance is shown for pre-test on the left panel and post-test on the right panel.

For the novel sentences, the model included the fixed effect of training group (treatment-coded, with the short training group as the reference level) and test session (dummy-coded; 0 = pre-test, 1 = post-test). The random effects structure consisted of random intercepts by subject, random intercepts by sentence, and random intercepts by talker. There were no statistically reliable differences between the short group and the medium training group ($\hat{\beta} = 0.000$, $SE = 0.032$, $t = -0.003$, $p = 0.998$) nor was there a statistically reliable difference between the short group and the long group ($\hat{\beta} = -0.003$, $SE = 0.003$, $t = -0.111$, $p = 0.912$). There was a statistically significant effect of test session ($\hat{\beta} = 0.055$, $SE = 0.007$, $t = 6.880$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that participants showed

higher performance at post-test compared to pre-test. All other two- and three-way interactions were not statistically reliable (see Table III for model output).

Figure 6: Mean proportion accuracy for novel sentences for each of the three training groups for anomalous sentences. Performance is shown for pre-test on the left panel and post-test on the right panel.

IV. Discussion

In the current study, we examined the effect of different training durations on the adaption of noise-vocoded speech. Normal Hearing Listeners were trained to interpret noise-vocoded speech with feedback and completed testing on trained and novel items before training and immediately after training. Critically, participants were assigned to three different groups and they each received a different amount of training. The goal of

this design was to (1) assess the effect of training and compare the outcome of different amounts of training and (2) to examine the difference in performance between item type (sentences). Overall, we found that participants in all three groups displayed significant amount of improvement from pre-test to post-test. All three groups showed improvement at an equal rate meaning, the magnitude of improvement was similar across all training groups. Despite, receiving different amounts of training the short training group performed just as well as the medium and long training group. Additionally, this study assessed whether our participants could apply what they had learned in the training phase and apply it to the testing phase. The task in the training phase was considerably less demanding than the task presented in the testing phase of this study. Nonetheless, participants were able to show improvement when exposed to novel sentences, thus suggesting that learning and generalization had occurred. The results reflected that training could generalize to listening tasks that differ from the training (Tremblay et al., 1997). In terms of item type, participants did not exhibit any of reliable difference in performance between high-predictability sentences and low-predictability sentences. We discuss each finding in detail in the sections below.

Effect of training and different training durations

We observed a robust perceptual learning effect for listeners trained to interpret and process noise-vocoded sentences. Listeners in all three training groups made significant improvements from pre-test to post-test. Our results replicated previous findings demonstrating that exposure to auditory training will lead to an improvement in degraded speech comprehension (Davis et al., 2005; Hervais-Adelman et al., 2008; Loebach et al., 2008). Specifically, Davis (2005) displayed that written feedback in the

form of correct transcription helped promote learning for noise-vocoded sentences. In our paradigm, specifically during the training phase, listeners received a written presentation of two sentences accompanied by the presentation of an auditory stimuli. Once the participants had identified which of the two sentence they had just heard and they made their selection, feedback was immediately provided. By providing participants with written transcription, top-down processing was able to take effect and it allowed listeners to process degraded signal with the assistance of sentence context. Speech perception was evidently improved from pre-test and post-test across all training groups, despite the difference in training length. Gains were clearly reflected based on pre-test to post-test comparisons and all of the training groups were improving at a similar rate. Our results indicated that a short amount of training can be just as beneficial and can produce the same amount of improvement as a longer training dosage. Essentially, it didn't matter that we tripled the exposure and practice for the long training group, it's more important to provide an auditory training paradigm that is well-structured and provides clear feedback. We found no evidence that the amount of training influences immediate degraded speech comprehension. To be more specific, we found that more training did not provide an advantage.

Our results aligned with previous findings, accuracy for trained items was higher in comparison to accuracy for novel items. Although participants improved in terms of accuracy for both novel and trained items, performance for trained items was better. These findings replicate previous findings across various similar studies (Loebach et al., 2008). Listeners showcased better performance on trained items compared to novel items which likely signifies that they were more familiar with the trained items since this type

of stimuli had been presented in abundance during training. The increase in performance, across all stimuli type and phases of the study, implied that generalization occurred, and participants were able to apply what they learned from their training period to the post-test (Davis et al., 2005; Loebach et al., 2008). Similarly, at post-test, participants were able to demonstrate an enhanced understanding of noise-vocoded speech as shown by the fact that their training task was not as demanding as their testing task. Although, the subjects of this study were trained with a multiple-choice assignment they were able to showcase the benefits of training when given a transcription task. Comprehension of noise-vocoded speech was clearly displayed during the post-test. We take these findings as evidence that training periods that contain clear feedback, written transcription, and are well-structured promote learning and generalization of noise-vocoded speech.

Role of different item type presentation

In our study, we examined the differences in performance between the different item types, in other words we used different sentences to test the effectiveness of training and the importance of sentence context. As previously mentioned, low-predictability and high-predictability sentences were presented in all three phases of the experiment, which meant that our participants had been exposed to these sentences the most, thus increasing their familiarity with these item types. Whereas anomalous sentences were only present during the testing phases and served to determine the effect of training and to account for possibility that our participants were just memorizing the answers. LP and HP sentences were considered our trained items and our AN sentences were considered our novel sentences. For our trained items, results at training indicated that the short, medium, and long training groups all performed similarly in terms of correctly identifying HP and LP

sentences. There was no significant difference between the item types despite the fact that HP sentences carry semantically correlated information which makes keywords more predictable (Kalikow et al., 1977). At pre-test and post-test, all three groups performed comparably across both item types. Although, there was improvement seen from pre-test to post-test for both sentences, the gains were similar meaning that once again there was no difference in accuracy for LP and HP sentences. The fact that low-predictability sentence contains context that is not meaningful means it was harder to anticipate the words within the phrase, yet our participants were still able to identify these types of sentences at a similar rate as high-predictability sentences. There was no significant difference between sentence type, in terms of proportion correct between LP and HP sentences. Regarding novel sentences, the result patterns indicated that training was effective and that our participants did show benefit from receiving training. Although our novel sentences contain words that don't go together, participants were still able to showcase improvement from pre-test to post-test. These results reflected that learning had occurred and degraded speech comprehension had been enhanced. Our findings indicated that all three different types of stimuli led to improved speech recognition skills, despite the fact that some of the sentence did not carry meaningful context, and it suggested that training can lead to beneficial gains.

Clinical implications and future directions

Auditory training is becoming an integral aspect of the aural rehabilitation treatment plans created by clinicians, due to its promising outcomes. Our results align with the idea that exposing normal hearing individuals to artificially distorted speech will

lead to improvements in participants' speech recognition skills and overall speech comprehension. This finding is supported by the fact that previously unintelligible words are better understood after they've been presented with a sufficient amount of training (Davis et al., 2005). Similarly, CI users would benefit from this type of exposure and a well-structured auditory training paradigm in order to improve their ability to perceive the acoustic signal that is transmitted through their surgically implanted device.

Currently, there is no formally agreed upon or widely accepted standardized recommendation that can be applied to all CI patients with hearing loss. Other studies have focused on understanding the factors that influence the adaptation of noise-vocoded speech but, very few have focused on defining the optimal parameters that leads to the most improvement and produces beneficial gains. This study emphasizes the importance of implementing a training program that provides clear feedback and is strategically organized. Specifically, it is crucial to provide participants with a training session that is designed to promote learning and generalization, as well as speech recognition gains.

Clinicians are given limited therapy time with their patients, so they must ensure that their therapy plan will fit within the therapy session and will help the patient achieve their goals. Clinicians intend for their patients to be able to translate the skills they learn during training and apply them to novel presentations of degraded speech. This study lays the foundation for how future rehabilitation programs should be designed, supports the inclusion of auditory training, and suggests that a longer training dosage doesn't necessarily result in better learning outcomes. Rehabilitation programs center around helping individuals learn to hear, interpret, and understand the new signals that are being presented to them. The present study takes a significant step in the right direction in terms

of learning how to refine and enhance a CI user's ability to adjust to their devices and improve their degraded speech comprehension. Future research is aimed at understanding the relationship between speech-in noise performance and speech perception (Yeend et al., 2017). Learning how to improve speech understanding in noise for normal hearing listeners or for people with noise exposure, may contribute to the reduction of CI user's speech perception variability.

To further understand auditory training and the factors that affect training outcomes, researchers have conducted studies that examined the effectiveness of presenting audiovisual cues and written cues in order to facilitate speech recognition (Pilling & Thomas, 2011). Similar studies have focused on the effect that adverse conditions and the presence of noise has on speech perception. For example, individuals are more likely to adjust to the additive noise if they are tasked with identifying a real word underneath the noise instead of nonwords (Lecumberri et al., 2010). A limitation of the current study is that participants were presented with noise-vocoded speech in a somewhat controlled setting, and they were tasked with focusing on the degraded speech itself without any outside noise interrupting their concentration. In a public setting, a CI user might struggle to translate their training due to the fact they were trained in a quiet environment. Although CI users can perform well in quiet environments, they tend to have difficulty understanding speech in demanding listening conditions because of the increased need for more spectral channels (Dingemanse & Goedegebure, 2019). The use of a more natural setting with background noise will enhance generalization and will indicate how well a CI user can adapt in a more demanding setting. Another limitation of this study was only displaying our participants with two multiple choice options for the

training phase. To make the training phase more challenging and to ensure that our participants were understanding the phrase being presented to them, we should have added 1-2 more options. A strength of the current design was the inclusion of multiple talkers from different regions. Processing unfamiliar accent requires increased listening effort and activates neural mechanism to help distinguish accent variation and other distortions (Adank et al., 2015). The listeners in this study were exposed to multiple accents from different US regions and were expected to adapt to the differences in production of both phonemes and words. Lastly, the inclusion of a post-test at a later time will strengthen the validity and reliability of this study's results.

Acknowledgments/Dedication

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To my family and friends, thank you for being patient with me and for your unwavering encouragement. Having you all in my life has made it easier to stay motivated and determined throughout my undergraduate career.

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research skills. This project is the product of countless hours of our hard work, and I could not have asked for a better mentor.

Future Use

This honors thesis was completed in preparation for manuscript submission. Sections of this thesis may be used for the development and submission of a manuscript for publication.

Supplemental Material

Table I. Training results of the mixed effects model for training groups and sentence predictability. As described in the main text, training condition was treatment-coded with short training as the reference level, yielding two contrasts for training condition (short vs. medium, short vs. long). Predictability was dummy-coded (0 = low predictability sentences, 1 = high predictability sentences).

Fixed effect	$\hat{\beta}$	<i>SE</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	6.466	0.875	7.392	<0.001
Short vs. Medium	-0.480	0.965	-0.498	0.619
Short vs. Long	-1.063	0.917	-1.159	0.246
Predictability	0.758	0.891	0.851	0.395

Short vs. Medium x Predictability	-0.535	1.008	-0.530	0.596
Short vs. Long x Predictability	-0.570	0.937	-0.608	0.543

Table II. Test results of the mixed effects model for trained sentences for training groups, sentence predictability, and test session. As described in the main text, training condition was treatment-coded with short training as the reference level, yielding two contrasts for training condition (short vs. medium, short vs. long). Test session was dummy-coded (0 = pre-test, 1 = post-test). Predictability was dummy-coded (0 = low predictability sentences, 1 = high predictability sentences).

Fixed effect	$\hat{\beta}$	<i>SE</i>	<i>DF</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	0.779	0.058	11.65	13.489	<0.001
Short vs. Medium	0.007	0.034	86.54	0.214	0.831
Short vs. Long	0.007	0.035	86.55	0.204	0.837
Test	0.127	0.016	455.5	7.717	<0.001
Predictability	-0.015	0.021	563.2	-0.723	0.470
Short vs. Medium x Test	-0.021	0.023	455.7	-0.903	0.367
Short vs. Long x Test	-0.027	0.024	457.1	-1.113	0.266
Short vs. Medium x Predictability	-0.027	0.024	301.8	-1.091	-0.276
Short vs. Long x Predictability	-0.063	0.026	301.9	-2.451	0.015
Test x Predictability	-0.007	0.017	2957	-0.414	0.679

Short vs. Medium x Test x Predictability	0.018	0.023	2956	0.786	0.432
Short vs. Long x Test x Predictability	-0.003	0.024	2957	-0.132	0.895

Table III. Test results of the mixed effects model for novel sentences for training groups and test session. As described in the main text, training condition was treatment-coded with short training as the reference level, yielding two contrasts for training condition (short vs. medium, short vs. long). Test session was dummy-coded (0 = pre-test, 1 = post-test).

Fixed effect	$\hat{\beta}$	<i>SE</i>	<i>DF</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	0.547	0.061	5.411	8.968	<0.001
Short vs. Medium	0.000	0.032	78.00	-0.003	0.998
Short vs. Long	-0.003	0.003	78.00	-0.111	0.912
Test	0.055	0.007	76.79	6.880	<0.001
Short vs. Medium x Test	0.017	0.011	76.79	1.536	0.129
Short vs. Long x Test	0.012	0.012	76.81	1.017	0.313

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